

Chemical Examination of *Echinops echinatus*

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β -amyrin, lupeol, hentriacontane and hentricontanol have been isolated from the extracts of *Echinops echinatus*.

*Echinops echinatus*¹ (Gokru, Compositae) is reported to be used as nerve tonic, in hoarse cough, hysteria and ophthalmia. Earlier investigations on *Echinops ritro*² and *E. sphaerocephalus*³ have led to the isolation of an alkaloid, echinopsine. As no further studies have been reported, the chemical investigation on this plant was undertaken. The plant material for these purposes was collected locally. Fresh plant was allowed to dry at room temperature for 15 days. The powdered, air dried plant (10 kg) was then percolated in the cold with 70% alcohol (15 litres). The alcoholic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to yield a dark green residue. It was treated with 5% HCl to remove alkaloids and then partitioned between benzene and 70% alcohol. Concentration of the benzene layer yielded a dark green semisolid. It was saponified to remove fatty material. The saponified material was extracted with ether, the removal of which gave 180 gm. of a white crude solid. (Positive Noller reaction⁴, Liebermann—Burchard test and tetranitromethane test). A portion of it (10 gm.) was chromatographed over alumina. Elution with hexane yielded a crystalline solid, m. p. 68-70° (Found, C, 84.90; H, 13.99%. C₃₁H₆₄ requires C, 85.33; H, 14.16%). This compound was a saturated hydrocarbon and was identified as *hentriacontane* through a mixed m.p. determination with an authentic sample. Subsequent elution with hexane-benzene (1:3) yielded hentricontanol, m. p. 85-87° (Found: C, 82.20; H, 14.41%. C₃₁H₆₄O requires C, 82.08; H, 14.16%) acetate, m. p. 75° (Found C, 80.64; H, 13.21%. C₃₃H₆₆O₂ requires C, 80.40; H, 13.40%).

Further elution of alumina column with benzene yielded a mixture of two substances β -amyrin and lupeol, and pure lupeol. Although this mixture gave a single spot on T.L.C. in several solvent systems, it did not give a sharp m.p. (168-75°). The separation, however, was effected by chromatography of the benzoate on alumina hexane-benzene (9:1). Before chromatography, this benzoate gave two spots on T.L.C. The pure benzoates after debenzoylation gave pure β -amyrin and lupeol.

β -amyrin: Crystallisation from acetone-methanol; m.p. 197-98° (α)_D + 90° (CHCl₃) (Found C, 84.08; H, 11.82%. C₃₀H₅₀O requires C 84.53; H, 11.73%). $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3268, 1381, 1359 and 819 cm⁻¹ assignable to OH, gemdimethyl and tri-substituted double bond functions. The ultra violet absorption spectrum of the substance had no maxima above 212 m μ . It gave a yellow colouration with tetranitromethane showing the presence of

1. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayar, and I. C. Chopra, *Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants*, 1956, 104.
2. A. D. Turova, B. S. Nikol'skaya and E. A. Trutneva. *Farmakoli. Toksikol.*, 1957, **20**, No. 3, 23-9.
3. I. K. Sukhoimut. *Apteknoe Delo*, 1960, **9**, No. 1, 62-7.
4. C. R. Noller, R. A. Smith, G. H. Harris and J. W. Walker, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 3047.

unsaturation in the molecule and a positive Noller reaction with commercial thionyl chloride suggesting the possibility of its being a triterpenoid. The identity of this compound with β -amyrin was suggested by the physical properties of this compound, its benzoate, m.p. 231-32° and its infra red spectrum and was confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample of β -amyrin.

Lupeol: Crystallised from acetone-methanol, m.p. 215-16° (α)_D +19° (CHCl₃) (Found C, 84.46; H, 10.14%. C₃₀H₅₀O requires C, 84.53; H, 11.73%). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3322, 1637, and 882 cm⁻¹ assignable to OH and isopropenyl¹⁵ functions. The ultra violet absorption spectrum of the substance had no maxima above 212 m μ . It gave a yellow colouration with tetranitromethane showing the presence of unsaturation in the molecule and a positive Noller reaction with commercial thionyl chloride suggesting the possibility of its being a triterpenoid. The identity of this compound with lupeol was suggested by the physical properties of this compound, its benzoate, ketone, hydrocarbon, hydrogenated product and its infra red spectrum and was confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample of lupeol.

Lupeol Benzoate: This was formed by the treatment of lupeol with benzoyl chloride and pyridine and was crystallised from chloroform-methanol, m.p. 275° (α)_D +65° (CHCl₃) (Found C, 83.55; H, 10.40%. C₃₇H₅₄O₂ requires C, 83.77%, H, 10.18%).

Lupenone: This was formed by the oxidation of lupeol in acetone with 8 N. Chromic acid solution (Zones reagent) and was crystallised from acetone-methanol, m.p. 171-72° (α)_D +60° (CHCl₃) (Found 84.80; H, 11.35%. C₃₀H₄₈O requires C, 84.95; H, 11.08%) $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1712 cm⁻¹.

Wolff-Kishner reduction of the Ketone: Lupenone on reduction with sodium, diethylene glycol and anhydrous hydrazine gave a hydrocarbon which crystallised from methanol, m.p. 165-66° (α)_D +35° (CHCl₃) (Found C, 87.46; H, 12.73%. C₃₀H₅₀ requires C, 87.84; H, 12.19%).

Hydrogenated Lupeol: It was catalytically hydrogenated in presence of platinum black in dioxan solution, m.p. 201-2°. The absorption of hydrogen corresponds to the presence of one double bond.

Alcoholic residue after extraction with benzene gave tests for phenol. Further work on this residue could not be continued due to low yield.

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